

Exploring open access journal APC from a macroscopic perspective: International comparison between Taiwan and benchmark countries

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Introduction

Recently, European and American countries have exerted increasing influence on open access (OA) movements. For Taiwan to stipulate policies or regulations related to OA publication models, the current situation in Taiwan must be understood first. Israel, Switzerland, Sweden, the Netherlands, Finland, and Ireland, which have similar demographics and economies but have better scientific research performance, are selected as the subjects of six benchmark countries were compared to propose concrete and feasible forward-looking plans. Lately, the prosperous development of OA journal article processing charge (APC) mechanism has caused considerable controversy and concern (Samberg, Schneider, Taylor, & Wolfe, 2018) because APCs increase the already heavy burden on authors, research institutes, and research-funding bodies (Monson, Highby, & Rathe, 2014). In addition, libraries have difficulty discerning whether the subscription fees for individual hybrid OA journals have been lowered (Björk & Solomon, 2014; Willinsky & Rusk, 2019).

This study collected SCIE and SSCI indexed OA articles published by the seven countries and explored the following questions:

- (1) From 2016 to 2020, what were the distributions of OA articles in SCIE and SSCI journals and what were the trends of distribution over time in the six benchmark countries?
- (2) From 2016 to 2020, what were the distributions of OA SCIE and SSCI articles in terms of their APC amounts and what were the trends of distribution over time in the six benchmark countries?
- (3) From 2016 to 2020, which journals received the most APCs from OA publications in SCIE and SSCI journals in the six benchmark countries?

Methods

This study collected 504,624 research articles and review articles published under the OA model in Taiwan and the six benchmark countries between 2016 and 2020 from the SCIE and SSCI databases. The retrieval period ran from March 2021 to April 2021. In addition, the APCs for 8,761 OA journals were compiled and converted to U.S. Dollars in December 2020. Of the collected journals, 7,607 adopted fixed prices for APCs, and 433 were diamond OA journals free of APCs. The remaining 721 journals adopted an APC mechanism that did not correspond to individual

articles; thus, they were not within this study's research scope.

Research Results

Publication of OA journal articles in benchmark countries

Except for Israel, each of the benchmark countries has published more than 50% of their journal articles under the OA model from 2017 onward. Table 1 shows that over two-thirds (66.09%) of all published journal articles in the Netherlands in 2020 were OA articles.

Table 1. Countries and article publication distributions.

Country	Number of articles	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
Israel	# of A	14,937	15,085	15,824	17,288	18,584	
	# of OA A	5,539	5,817	6,217	6,505	6,880	30,958
	% of OA A	37.08%	38.56%	39.29%	37.63%	37.02%	
Switzerland	# of A	32,317	34,084	34,814	37,319	39,780	
	# of OA A	17,858	19,308	20,546	21,636	22,871	102,219
	% of OA A	55.26%	56.65%	59.02%	57.98%	57.49%	
Sweden	# of A	29,208	30,315	31,456	34,666	35,982	
	# of OA A	14,097	16,160	18,012	20,137	22,670	91,076
	% of OA A	48.26%	53.31%	57.26%	58.09%	63.00%	
The Netherlands	# of A	42,149	43,043	44,959	49,410	51,688	
	# of OA A	22,800	25,861	29,347	31,501	34,159	143,668
	% of OA A	54.09%	60.08%	65.28%	63.75%	66.09%	
Finland	# of A	13,910	14,105	14,611	16,243	17,180	
	# of OA A	6,716	8,287	9,466	10,610	10,652	45,731
	% of OA A	48.28%	58.75%	64.79%	65.32%	62.00%	
Ireland	# of A	11,288	11,814	12,737	14,283	15,684	
	# of OA A	5,632	6,191	7,054	7,633	7,888	34,398
	% of OA A	49.89%	52.40%	55.38%	53.44%	50.29%	
Taiwan	# of A	26,379	25,399	25,507	28,547	32,217	
	# of OA A	9,375	10,012	10,441	12,205	14,541	56,574
	% of OA A	35.54%	39.42%	40.93%	42.75%	45.13%	

of A= number of articles # of OA A=number of OA article

The number of journals containing OA articles increased over time in Switzerland, Sweden, and the Netherlands. Table 2 shows that the number of OA journals decreased in Israel, Finland, and Ireland in 2020; however, the corresponding numbers of journals in that year were substantially higher than their 2016 counterparts.

Table 2. Numbers of OA journals published in the countries.

Country	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
Israel	1,699	1,788	1,979	2,017	1,942	4,292
Switzerland	3,629	3,899	4,094	4,145	4,222	7,286
Sweden	3,251	3,645	4,099	4,396	4,677	7,472
The Netherlands	4,323	4,905	5,334	5,510	5,688	8,479
Finland	2,260	2,846	3,183	3,327	3,263	6,127
Ireland	2,205	2,379	2,655	2,714	2,675	5,609
Taiwan	1,737	1,869	1,990	2,065	2,079	4,249

Overview of APCs in relation to OA journal articles in benchmark countries

This study calculated APCs for only journals that collected fixed APCs. In Table 3, the Netherlands had the highest number of articles published, hence the highest APCs, per year for the whole study period.

Table 3. Total amount of fixed APCs.

	Total amount \$	Average APC per A	
		All	Excluding diamond OA
Israel	72,378,091.30	2,970	3,050
Switzerland	245,964,106.74	2,995	3,088
Sweden	216,569,730.35	2,994	3,056
The Netherlands	361,389,393.90	3,096	3,149
Finland	105,792,963.06	2,963	3,022
Ireland	78,877,037.77	2,987	3,045
Taiwan	85,787,498.38	2,436	2,542

To calculate the average APC per OA journal article in each country, articles published in diamond OA journals were excluded first. Table 4 shows that only minor differences were observed in the figures across all the benchmark countries. Taiwan had a relatively high proportion of articles being published in diamond OA journals (2.6%). The results of in-depth exploration revealed that most of the diamond OA journals were local journals.

Table 4. Average APC for each article published in journals with fixed APCs.

	# of A	fixed APCs		Proportion	
		All	Excluding diamond OA	All	Excluding diamond OA
Israel	30,958	24,368	23,727	78.71%	76.64%
Switzerland	102,219	82,118	79,663	80.34%	77.93%
Sweden	91,076	72,330	70,861	79.42%	77.80%
The Netherlands	143,668	116,733	114,779	81.25%	79.89%
Finland	45,731	35,708	35,013	78.08%	76.56%
Ireland	34,398	26,411	25,901	76.78%	75.30%
Taiwan	56,574	35,216	33,743	62.25%	59.64%

Total fees paid to OA journal

This study analyzed over 7000 journals, because of the enormous quantity of data involved, only the top three journals of each country are listed in this paper. Table 5 shows that in all seven countries, the top two journals were mega journals *Scientific Reports* and *PLOS ONE* in either order. In addition, the publication quantities of these two journals exceeded those of all other journals in all seven countries.

Table 5. Top three fixed-APC journals with the highest APC incomes.

Country	Journal	# of A	\$ Amount
Israel	1 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	1,107	2,070,090
	2 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	846	1,433,970
	3 <i>NATURE COMMUNICATIONS</i>	598	3,217,240
Switzerland	1 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	2,738	4,640,910
	2 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	2,708	5,063,960
	3 <i>NATURE COMMUNICATIONS</i>	1,723	9,269,740
Sweden	1 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	2,825	5,282,750
	2 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	2,588	4,386,660
	3 <i>NATURE COMMUNICATIONS</i>	1,046	5,627,480

The Netherlands	1 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	4,027	6,825,765
	2 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	2,826	5,284,620
	3 <i>ASTRONOMY & ASTROPHYSICS</i>	1,611	4,236,608
Finland	1 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	1,266	2,367,420
	2 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	873	1,479,735
	3 <i>ASTRONOMY & ASTROPHYSICS</i>	461	1,212,338
Ireland	1 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	886	1,656,820
	2 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	666	1,128,870
	3 <i>ASTRONOMY & ASTROPHYSICS</i>	434	1,141,333
Taiwan	1 <i>SCIENTIFIC REPORTS</i>	3,121	5,836,270
	2 <i>PLOS ONE</i>	2,255	3,822,225
	3 <i>MEDICINE</i>	1,370	3,753,800

Discussion

Except for Israel, all the benchmark countries had more than 50% of journal articles published under the OA model from 2017 onward, with the percentage in the Netherlands reaching 66.09% in 2020. Authors from the Netherlands, Sweden, and Switzerland exhibited the most diverse ranges of journals in their manuscript submission; thus, the numbers of journals containing OA articles were higher in these countries. In each of the five European benchmark countries, the proportion of OA journal articles exceeded that of articles published in the traditional model, and this is a noteworthy phenomenon. If Taiwan intends to stipulate national policies or regulations for OA publications, it must pay close and consistent attention to the subsequent OA movements in European countries.

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